

THE ORGANIZATION OF METEOROLOGICAL OBSERVATIONS AT THE WATER BALANCE STATION IN THE REPUBLIC OF BASHKORTOSTAN

Komissarov A.

Doctor of Agricultural Sciences

Minniakhmetov I.

Candidate of Agricultural Sciences

Abstract

The article describes the organization of meteorological observations at a meteorological station located in the Ufa district of the Republic of Bashkortostan, as well as the available instruments, equipment, and documentation used to record the results of these observations. Meteorological data is collected according to a program officially registered with the Bashkir Hydrometeorological and Environmental Monitoring Agency. The article presents meteorological indicators collected during the period from 2000 to 2023.

Keywords: meteorological post, precipitation, air temperature, instrument verification, thermometer, precipitation meter, snow measuring rails, water balance station, license.

The first meteorological observations in Bashkiria began in the late 18th century and were conducted by individual enthusiasts, such as local historian Rebellinsky and pharmacist Bosse. Since 1838, these observations have been conducted at the men's gymnasium, which is now the site of the medical university. In 1912, meteorological measurements began at a station located on the southwestern edge of Ufa, near the television center. In 1875, the first observations were recorded in the city of Birsik and at the Blagoveshchensk factory, as well as at the Belebeevskaya agricultural school on the territory of Bashkortostan. Currently, there are 32 meteorological stations and four meteorological posts operating in the republic [1].

The Water Balance Station (VBS) is a structural unit of the Federal State Budget Institution "Management of Bashmeliovodkhoz" and the Department of

Production of the Bashkir State Agrarian University. It is located on the territory of the Dmitrievsky Village Council of the Ufa Municipal District, 3 kilometers southeast of the Podymalovo village.

The main purpose of the VBS is to conduct comprehensive climate, hydrology, soil ecology, and hydro-reclamation research in order to develop effective land use systems in the Republic of Bashkortostan. Additionally, the VBS serves as a platform for conducting field studies, educational and industrial training, and the formation of professional competencies in the fields of "Land Management and Cadastres" and "Environmental Management and Water Use" [3, p.28]. The VBS has been operating since 2000.

The VBS includes a meteorological and lysimetric station, an evaporative pool, a laboratory, utility rooms, and regime wells (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Plan of the Water Balance Station

A - office space; B – security office; C - training area; D – storage area; E – parking garage; F – utility room; G – basement.

1. Wind meter; 2. Snow measuring rail; 3. Danilin permafrost meter; 4. Tret'yakov sedimentation meter; 5. Selyaninov psychrometric booth; 6. GGI-3000 rain

gauge; 7. GGI-3000 evaporator; 8. Ice machine; 9. Automated weather station; 91. Lysimeter; 10. Scales 2t; 11. Soil evaporators GGI-500-100; 12. Tensiometers; 13. Wells; 14. Background culture (perennial grasses);

15. Water tank; 16. Laboratory; 17. Pipe for discharging water from the evaporator pool; 18. Transformer substation; 19. Experimental plots with agricultural crops.

The area of the land plot where VBS is located is 6,000 square meters. In the immediate vicinity of VBS, there are experimental fields where field experiments with various agricultural crops are conducted. During the period from 2001 to 2023, studies were carried out to investigate the effects of organic and mineral fertilizers, irrigation regimes, and irrigation methods on the yields of onions, perennial grasses (e.g., eastern goatgrass, boneless grass, alfalfa), sugar beets, soybeans, and potatoes [7, p.18, 8, p. 42, 9, p. 22, 10, p. 47, 11, p. 53, 12, p. 33, 13, p. 49, 14, p.194].

Meteorological observations at VBS are conducted in accordance with the program of the meteorological station, which is officially registered with the Bashkir Hydrometeorological and Environmental Monitoring Administration under the number 545005545, and is known as the Dmitrievsky Meteorological Station (Figure 2). Meteorological events are monitored in accordance with regulations [4, p.15], using a standard set of instruments [5, p.12].

The following devices and equipment are located

Figure 2 Dmitrievsky Meteorological Station

Meteorological observations are measurements of various meteorological factors, such as temperature (maximum, minimum, and current), precipitation, and other atmospheric conditions. These observations are taken twice a day, at 8 a.m. and 8 p.m., by observers at the meteorological station. The observations last for 10 minutes, ending exactly on the hour specified [6, p.14].

To record the observations, the station has special tables (TLC-1 and TM-8) and books (KM-5) available. At the end of each month, the TM-8 table is sent to Bashhydromet, providing information on daily maximum and minimum temperatures, precipitation, and atmospheric phenomena.

During the period with snow cover, daily measurements of snow depth are taken on three permanent

at the meteorological station: a wind meter, a snow measuring rail, a Danilin permafrost meter, an O-1 Tretyakov sedimentation meter, a psychrometric booth, a GGI-3000 evaporator, and an ice machine.

The psychrometric booth is used to house and protect the maximum and minimum thermometers and the urgent thermometer, which measure air temperature. These thermometers are protected from direct exposure to sunlight, radiation from surrounding objects, precipitation, and strong gusts of wind.

FSBI «Bashmeliovodkhoz» has an indefinite license to operate this equipment, for the right to conduct meteorological observations, issued by Roshydromet, in accordance with the order of the Ministry of Natural Resources and Ecology of the Russian Federation No. 509 dated 30.07.2020 "On Approval of the Procedure for Legal Entities and Individuals Collecting Information on Environmental Conditions and Pollution to the Federal Service for Hydrometeorology and Monitoring of Information about Man-Made Emergencies, which have, are providing, or may have a Negative Impact on the Environment". Information obtained as a result of meteorological observations is sent to Bashhydromet (Figure 2).

measuring rails (C1, C2, C3). Additionally, route measurements in the field and forest are conducted once a decade during snow cover and once every 5 days during snowmelt.

The KM-5 form is filled out with information about the height of the snow cover, the density of snow, the amount of water in the snow pack, the extent of snow cover around the route, the type of snow cover, and the condition of the snow. TLC-1 is a table of meteorological and agrometeorological observations (decadal). It is filled in every week on the 11th and 21st of each month to check and evaluate the work of the meteorological post. After verification, one copy of the table with comments is returned to the observation point and stored in the archive of the meteorological post.

The table consists of two pages. The first page contains meteorological information for the decade and

a description of the main meteorological features, as well as the results of maximum and minimum air temperature observations. The second page contains results of precipitation observations, including overnight, day, and day totals.

In addition to the meteorological observations mentioned above, which are transmitted to Bashhydromet, further meteorological measurements of air humidity, atmospheric pressure, water surface evaporation, soil freezing depth and soil moisture are also taken at VBS.

Data on precipitation, soil moisture, temperature and relative humidity during the growing season allows us to assess the level of dryness of the climate in the region and to justify the need for specific hydrological measures. During the observation period, the 2010 growing season was unusually dry, with only 112 millimeters of precipitation between May and August, and a total of 2,519 degrees Celsius above 10 degrees Celsius. The wettest growing season was in 2002, with 309 millimeters of rainfall and 1,981 degrees Celsius, respectively.

The water reserves in the snow cover and the depth of soil freezing prior to the start of snowmelt are both important factors for predicting the magnitude of spring flood runoff. During the period from 2001 to 2023, the lowest soil freezing (15 centimeters) was recorded in the winter of 2015-2016, while the highest (84 centimeters) occurred in March 2009.

The height of the snow cover, according to route snow surveys, was the highest in the first ten days of March 2001, reaching 72 centimeters in open fields and 103 centimeters in forests. Moisture reserves in the snow were also at their maximum during this period, amounting to 210 millimeters and 280 millimeters, respectively. Conversely, the lowest figures were recorded in 2009, with a snow height of 29 centimeters and 38 centimeters, respectively, and water content in the snow of 71 millimeters and 82 millimeters, respectively.

Measuring instruments at a specialized weather station that collect meteorological data, such as thermometers, snow measurement rails, and a snow density meter, are subject to mandatory verification by the Bashkir Hydrometeorological and Environmental Monitoring Department. After the verification process by the instrument service and measuring equipment verification team, a verification certificate is issued indicating the validity period. The calibration intervals for these devices vary: 3 years for thermometers, 2 years for snow measurement rails, and 1 year for the snow density meter.

The data collected from these instruments is used for scientific research and to provide operational information and guidance on irrigation practices for agricultural crops to agronomic services in nearby farms.

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